

The Clinical Feature of Chronic Hepatitis B Patients with High HBV pgRNA

Yunzhe Zhang¹, Xuezhong Lei^{1,#}

¹Center of Infectious Diseases, West China Hospital, Sichuan University, Chengdu 610041, China

Background and Aims: At present, nucleos(t)ide analogue (NA) is usually used to treat chronic hepatitis B, but there are still some patients with high levels of pgRNA after long-term treatment. We tried to study the clinical characteristics of this part of the population.

Methods: A total of 211 patients who had been treated with NAs for more than one year and had been followed up in our outpatient department for a long time were included in the study. The concentrations of HBV serological (HBsAg, HBeAg, HBV DNA, anti-HBe) /biochemical indicators (ALT, AST, GGT, AFP) were measured in this study.

Results: ALT/AST/HBV DNA/HBsAg in high pgRNA group was significantly higher than those in low pgRNA group, and the HBeAg negative rate of high pgRNA group was much lower than that of low pgRNA group.

Conclusion: CHB patients with high pgRNA are more likely to have relatively active viruses and more severe liver inflammation. In addition, in terms of virological response, the proportion of HBeAg negative in high pgRNA population is significantly higher than that in low pgRNA population, and the titer of HBsAg is significantly higher than that of people with low pgRNA.

Keywords: pgRNA; Patients; HBeAg; Nucleos(t)ide analogue; HBsAg.

Background

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is still a worldwide public health problem. There are still HBV chronic infected people. At present, the treatment for HBV is mainly by using nucleos(t)ide analogue (NA) and interferon. Due to the serious side effects of interferon, NAs is more often used in clinical treatment. NAs mainly inhibits the reverse transcription of pre - genomic RNA (pgRNA) into HBV DNA, thereby inhibiting the synthesis of HBV DNA, but does not affect the synthesis of HBV pgRNA. NAs can improve long-term prognosis and reduce the risk of liver cirrhosis and even hepatocellular carcinoma. However, due to the lack of direct antiviral effect of NAs on cccDNA, HBV infection cannot be completely eliminated. In view of the fact that NAs has no or little effect on the transcriptional activity of cccDNA, even if the HBV DNA level is lower than the detection limit after treatment, HBV RNA is still produced under NA. Therefore, HBV RNA, especially pgRNA, may be a new potential marker for monitoring cccDNA activity in chronic hepatitis B^[1-5].

At present, there is still controversy about the end point of treatment for patients treated with NAs for a long time. According to the latest CHB guidelines of the American Association for the study of liver diseases (AASLD), when oral antiviral drugs are used, HBeAg seroconversion may be an indication to discontinue treatment^[2]. Some studies have shown that HBV pgRNA positive patients are related to the high risk of HBeAg clearance

failure^[3]. Another study suggests that HBV pgRNA can reflect the activity of cccDNA to a certain extent, that is, people with high pgRNA are more likely to relapse after drug withdrawal^[4].

As for the population whose long-term NA treatment still fails to reach the low pgRNA level, so far, there has been no further study on the treatment of this kind of population, including treatment scheme, risk factors and short-term and long-term prognosis analysis. This study monitored the status of HBV DNA, ALT and HBeAg in this population, trying to study the clinical characteristics of high pgRNA population.

Patients and Methods

Patients

This study began on December 1, 2020 and ended on April 1, 2022. The longest duration of treatment in the patient group was 43 months and the shortest was 13 months. Inclusion criteria: 1. Receiving Entecavir (ETV), Tenofovir alafenamide Fumarate (TAF) or tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TDF) treatment for more than one year. 2. patients who are regularly followed up in our outpatient department every 3–6 months. Exclusion criteria: 1. Patients < 18 years old; 2. patients with liver sclerosis and malignant tumor; 3. patients with other immunodeficiency diseases; 4. patients with incomplete data. If a patient changes drugs midway, it shall be classified according to the treatment received at the time of sampling. And 9 patients with SLE or long-term hormone taking history, 7 patients with hepatocellular carcinoma were excluded. The comparison of included and excluded patients are listed in Table 1.

Blood tests and serum viral markers

Since most patients cannot provide their baseline information at

Correspondence: Xuezhong Lei. E-mail: 18980601317@163.com. Address: Center of Infectious Diseases, West China Hospital, Sichuan University, Chengdu 610041, China.

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the beginning of treatment, the blood sample collection of all patients in this study is concentrated between January and March 2022, which is a single sample collection, so this study is a cross-sectional study. The biochemical indicators detected in this study mainly include alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase (AST), γ -glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT) and alpha fetoprotein (AFP). The serological markers reflecting HBV infection, including HBsAg, HBeAg, HBV DNA and anti-HBe, were determined in the same laboratory of West China Hospital of Sichuan University.

Table 1. The characteristics of included and excluded patients.

Characteristics	Included patients (n = 195)	Excluded patients (n = 16)	P value
Gender (male/female)	137/58	11/5	1.00
Age (yr)	43.77 \pm 10.69	42.68 \pm 11.23	0.871
Treatment (ETV/TDF/TAF)	86/92/17	7/7/2	0.873
Treatment time (month)	23.47 \pm 6.55	24.41 \pm 7.12	0.142

Quantification of HBV RNA

The quantification of HBV RNA is divided into nucleic acid capture and real-time fluorescence Nucleic acid thermostatic amplification detection according to the manufacturer's instructions (RenDu Biotech, Beijing, China). Nucleic acid capture is the specific capture of targets by magnetic particles in viral nucleic acid extracts RNA, forming a complex of magnetic particles and target RNA, and transferring the complex from the magnetic particles are separated from this one and then cleaned with washing liquid to obtain pure magnetic particles and complex of target RNA. The complex of the magnetic particle and the target RNA enters the amplification detection system.

Simple amplification and Testing (SAT) is a method of RNA transcription amplification and real-time detection using probes. The primer with T7 sequence binds to the target RNA and is produced under the action of reverse transcriptase m-m₁v DNA copy of target nucleic acid (RNA); T7 RNA polymerase takes DNA copy as template. The plate produces multiple RNA products. The product RNA copy can continue to be used as a template for reverse transcription of new and continue to transcribe more RNA products. While circulating amplification, anti the specific probes in the response system can bind to RNA products. The probe is labeled with fluorescent groups and a quenching group that is very close to the fluorescent group when the probe is not bound to the RNA product, inhibit fluorescence generation; When the probe is combined with the RNA product, fluorescent groups emit fluorescent signals. The more RNA products the more probes hybridize with the products, the stronger the fluorescence signal emitted. The detection instrument can detect the emitted fluorescence signal in real time. Bright the reaction time for the optical signal to reach a specific threshold is proportional to the initial concentration of target RNA. Every inverse Internal standard (IC) shall be provided for quality control samples during processing, amplification and detection. The concentration of the sample is calibrated by the software according to the target detection signal and IC signal of each reaction. The information

is determined after comparison.

Definition of high pgRNA

In the previous study of other institution, the virological and biochemical indexes of patients with pgRNA value ≥ 100 IU/mL were significantly different from those of patients with pgRNA value less than this value^[6]. So we stipulate patients who had achieved pgRNA ≥ 100 IU/mL were classified as high pgRNA group.

Data analysis

In this study, IBM SPSS statistics, version 18.0.0.1 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) was used for statistical analysis. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard value, and classified variables were expressed as frequency (percentage). Mann Whitney U test and chi square test for classification parameters were used to analyze the differences between subgroups to obtain statistical significance. All statistical tests were bilateral. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Result

Study population

We enrolled 195 eligible patients as the subjects of this study. A total of 70.3% (137/195) of the patients were men. The average age was 43.77 years. A total of 47.7% (93/195) of the patients were HBV pgRNA negative. The average treatment time is 23.47 \pm 6.55 months. The average alanine aminotransferase concentration was 44.99 IU/L, which was little higher than the normal value. A total of 21.5% (42/195) of the patients had elevated ALT (≥ 40 IU/L). The serum HBV DNA titer was 411.23 IU/mL on average, and 86, 92, and 17 patients were treated with ETV, TDF and TAF, respectively. According to whether pgRNA ≥ 100 IU/mL, the study population was divided into high pgRNA group and low pgRNA group, with 44 cases (22.6%) and 151 cases (77.4%) respectively.

Virological and biochemical characteristics of low and high pgRNA populations

The viral response and biochemical response of low and high pgRNA populations are listed in Table 2. We compared the gender and age of patients with high and low pgRNA, and found that there was no significant difference between them (both $P = 1.00$). But the treatment time of high pgRNA group was much lower than that of low pgRNA group (19.00 \pm 4.86 vs 24.77 \pm 6.42, $P < 0.01$). As for biochemical indicators, ALT in high pgRNA group was significantly higher than that in low pgRNA group (78.50 \pm 137.43 vs 35.23 \pm 60.42, $P = 0.048$), AST is also much higher than the other side (58.95 \pm 86.35 vs 28.52 \pm 24.49, $P = 0.025$). In addition, in terms of virological indicators, HBV DNA in high pgRNA group was significantly higher than that in low pgRNA group. (796.68 \pm 1360.89 vs 298.91 \pm 940.78, $P = 0.027$). Moreover, HBsAg in high pgRNA group was also higher than that in low pgRNA group (3302.74 \pm 6209.10, $P = 0.044$) and the HBeAg negative proportion of high pgRNA group was much lower than that of low pgRNA group (75.0% vs 95.4%, $P < 0.01$).

Table 2. The characteristics of enrolled patients.

Characteristics	High HBV pgRNA (n = 44)	Low HBV pgRNA (n = 151)	In total (n = 195)	P value
Gender (male/female)	30/14	107/44	137/58	1.00
Age (yr)	44.00 ± 9.76	43.70 ± 10.98	43.77 ± 10.69	0.86
Treatment (ETV/ TDF/TAF)	25/12/7	61/80/10	86/92/17	0.006
Treatment time (month)	19.00 ± 4.86	24.77 ± 6.42	23.47 ± 6.55	<0.01
HBeAg (IU/mL)	3302.74 ± 6209.10	1334.70 ± 1917.71	1778.83 ± 3474.04	0.044
ALT (IU/mL)	78.50 ± 137.43	35.23 ± 60.42	44.99 ± 85.66	0.048
AST (IU/mL)	58.95 ± 86.35	28.52 ± 24.49	35.39 ± 47.74	0.025
GGT (IU/mL)	49.36 ± 80.50	28.09 ± 31.53	32.89 ± 47.79	0.093
AFP (IU/mL)	12.71 ± 40.13	4.99 ± 14.96	6.31 ± 21.46	0.299
HBV DNA (IU/mL)	796.68 ± 1360.89	298.91 ± 940.78788	411.23 ± 1066.93	0.027

Discussion

Nowadays, people have paid much attention to pgRNA, a new indicator, which is usually regarded as an indicator reflecting the activity of cccDNA replication and guiding the timing of drug withdrawal or the evaluation of the prognosis of NA treatment^[1,3,4]. However, this study attempts to analyze the clinical characteristics of people who are still high in pgRNA after long-term NA treatment, so as to achieve the goal of early identification of such people at the initial stage of initiating NA treatment. Therefore, it is necessary to consider whether to use peg-IFN or peg-IFN combined with NA in the early stage of treatment to treat people with high pgRNA^[7]. In addition, due to the relatively limited clinical development of pgRNA, this study may have some significance in screening potential patients with high pgRNA in the population with chronic CHB infection. Moreover, it is of guiding significance to explore the reasons for the sustained high level of pgRNA in such patients.

The latest guidelines recommend NA treatment as the first-line treatment for CHB, which can significantly inhibit the replication of virus and the progress of liver inflammation, and can also reach the low level of pgRNA to a considerable extent. The data in this study clearly meet the description of the guidelines. Although NA treatment is effective, the economic burden of lifelong treatment can not be ignored, so the academic community has not stopped pursuing the withdrawal of NA treatment^[2]. However, at present, there are some disputes about the indication of discontinuation of NA treatment. Recent studies have shown that there is a considerable relationship between the pgRNA level of such patients and the recurrence of patients after drug withdrawal. People with high pgRNA are more likely to have recurrence and ALT flare^[4]. This study may be helpful to screen out the patients suitable for drug withdrawal. For the patients with high transaminase and HBV DNA, it is obvious that it is not appropriate to stop the drug due to the active viral replication and liver inflammation. For the patients who fails to achieve HBeAg clearance, this study supports the recommendation of the guidelines that such populations should not stop the treatment.

The data of this study showed that there was no significant difference in gender and age between the high pgRNA group and the low pgRNA group, while the ALT and HBV DNA of the high

pgRNA group were significantly higher than those of the low pgRNA group. It can be seen that people with high pgRNA are more likely to have relatively active viruses and more severe liver inflammation. In addition, in terms of virological response, the proportion of HBeAg negative in high pgRNA population is significantly higher than that in low pgRNA population. It's not hard for us to see that these two markers are associated with each other, suggesting that further research is needed to determine whether pgRNA level is a predictor of subsequent HBeAg. It should be noted that the proportion of patients treated with ETV with high pgRNA appears to be higher than those treated with TDF and TAF. This may suggest that we prefer TAF and TDF in the selection of NA oral drugs, but it may be related to the small sample size included in this study.

This study is a cross-sectional study. It lacks relevant data of patients before treatment and cannot be compared before and after treatment. Therefore, it has certain limitations. In addition, there is a lack of research on patients with high pgRNA in newly treated patients who have not yet started NA treatment, which needs to be further confirmed.

Abbreviations

AFP, fetoprotein; ALT, alanin0. e aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; CHB, chronic hepatitis B; ETV, entecavir; GGT, γ-glutamyl transpeptidase; HBV, Hepatitis B virus; NA, nucleos(t)ide analogue; pgRNA, pregenomic RNA; TAF, tenofovir alafenamide fumarate; TDF, tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

YZZ reviewed the literature and wrote the manuscript, searched the literature and reviewed the manuscript. XZL had overall responsibility for the study and wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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